

It was Portugal, not Brazil, that was fighting for its independence

between 1820 and 1834

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Preface

This article contains a mystery that will only be revealed to those who read it until the end.

Introduction

For the vast majority of Brazilians (who have some historical knowledge), Brazil's independence occurred on September 7, 1822. But we also know that it differs significantly from other emancipation processes in America. While the Spanish colonies and North America followed paths marked by intense conflicts and popular mobilizations, Brazil experienced a more unique process. This article proposes a reflection on Brazilian independence not as a traditional colonial liberation movement, but as an atypical phenomenon, which would possibly be better understood as an attempt at independence by the nation of Portugal to emancipate itself from the seat of imperial power in the figure of D. João VI, who in 1820 commanded his United Kingdom of Portugal, Brazil and Algarves from Rio de Janeiro, since 1808.

In 1808, the arrival of the Portuguese royal family in Brazil elevated the colony's status to the United Kingdom of Portugal, Brazil and Algarves, abolishing the colonial pact and transferring the empire's capital to Rio de Janeiro. This crucial event changed the economic and administrative bases of the territory, differentiating it from the other American colonies that were fighting for independence. Sérgio Buarque de Holanda observes that "the move of the court to Brazil created a new political and social dynamic, which moved Brazil away from the condition of a mere colony" (Holanda, 1936).

The catalyst for Brazilian independence did not emerge in Brazil, but in Portugal, with the Porto Revolution in 1820, which forced Dom João VI to return to Europe and left his son, Dom Pedro, as regent. This movement precipitated a series of events that culminated in the declaration of independence in 1822. However, unlike other independence processes, the transition of power in Brazil was marked less by intense wars and more by political maneuvers. According to Marcos Sorrilha, "Brazilian independence was a consequence of political transformations in Europe, reflected in the events that occurred in Portugal and in Dom Pedro's actions in Brazil" (Sorrilha, 2020).

This article presents a detailed analysis of the arguments that support the view of Brazilian independence as a unique process, highlighting the economic, political and social peculiarities that differentiate the Brazilian case from other American independence.

Below we will examine 5 arguments that defend this thesis:

Argument 1: The Status of Brazil Before Independence

Brazil's independence in 1822 must be analyzed in light of the significant changes that have occurred in the country since the arrival of the Portuguese royal family in 1808. The elevation of Brazil to the United Kingdom of Portugal, Brazil and Algarves abolished the colonial pact and transformed the dynamics political and economic of the territory. This differentiated status calls into question the idea of traditionally colonial independence.

Sérgio Buarque de Holanda highlights that "the transfer of the court to Brazil and the opening of ports to friendly nations not only modified the economic structure, but also created a new political configuration" (Holanda, 1936). This movement of administrative centralization in Rio de Janeiro turned Brazil into a seat of power, moving it away from the condition of a simple colony.

Furthermore, the Porto Revolution in 1820, which took place in Portugal, had a direct impact on Brazilian independence. The political and social pressures that arose in the metropolis culminated in the return of Dom João VI to Portugal, leaving his son, Dom Pedro, as prince regent in Brazil. Marcos Sorrilha observes that "the Porto Revolution was a crucial event that precipitated Brazilian independence, forcing a reconfiguration of power between Portugal and Brazil" (Sorrilha, 2020).

These events highlight that Brazil's independence process cannot be seen simply as a colonial rupture, but rather as a series of internal and external transformations that reconfigured the relationship between the metropolis and its former colony.

Argument 2: The War of Independence and Popular Participation

The Brazilian War of Independence is notable for its lower intensity and limited popular participation compared to other wars of independence in America, such as those in the United States, Haiti and Spanish colonies. This argument highlights how the nature and extent of the Brazilian war differs substantially from conflicts in other territories.

Popular participation in the Brazilian war of independence was relatively low. Although there were significant clashes, such as the battles in Bahia, the war did not mobilize the mass population in the same way that occurred in other American revolutions. Sérgio Buarque de Holanda mentions that "Brazilian independence was marked by an elitist character, with little participation from the popular classes" (Holanda, 1936).

Furthermore, the war in Brazil saw relatively little intense fighting and a lower death toll compared to the American and Haitian revolutions. The most notable peculiarity, however, was the extension of the conflict beyond Brazilian territory. After the defeat of Portuguese troops in Brazil, the Brazilian navy headed to Portugal to continue the conflict, something unprecedented in other wars of independence. Marcos Sorrilha observes that "the extension of the conflict to Portugal highlights a continuous effort to guarantee the power of the Bragança family, reflecting more of an internal struggle than a typical colonial liberation war" (Sorrilha, 2020).

The following table illustrates the comparison between the different wars of independence in America:

Country	Number of deaths	Number of Combatants	Duration (years)
U.S	25,000	200,000	1775-1783 (8 years)
Haiti	150,000	100,000	1791-1804 (13 years)
Brazil	6,000	20,000	1822-1824 (2 years)
Mexico	500,000	100,000	1810-1821 (11 years)
Gran Colombia	40,000	40,000	1810-1824 (14 years)
Cuba	200,000	100,000	1868-1898 (30 years)

Table 1 Sources:

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Argument 3: Formation of the Post-Independence Government

The formation of the Brazilian government after independence reveals a monarchical continuity that contrasts sharply with the republics established in other American colonies. This argument highlights how Brazil maintained a power structure similar to that existing before independence, rather than adopting a new governmental system.

In the United States, the War of Independence resulted in the creation of a democratic republic, reflecting intense popular participation and the desire for self-determination. In Spanish America, although the republics formed were more oligarchic, they still represented a significant break with colonial structures. In contrast, Brazil maintained the monarchy with Dom Pedro I, son of Dom João VI, ascending to the throne.

Sérgio Buarque de Holanda observes that "the continuity of the monarchy in Brazil after independence is a clear indication of the lack of a deeper social and political revolution" (Holanda, 1936). The maintenance of the same royal family in power, with the capital remaining in Rio de Janeiro, demonstrates that Brazilian independence was more a reconfiguration of existing power than a revolutionary transformation.

The Constitution of 1824, although it was the first Brazilian Constitution, reflected many elements of the Portuguese Constitution of 1822, created after the Liberal Revolution of Porto. This Constitution limited the absolute powers of the monarch, but in Brazil, the centralization of power remained significant, with Dom Pedro I exercising considerable control over the government.

Marcos Sorrilha points out that "the monarchical structure in post-independence Brazil reflected the continuity of elites in power, unlike republican movements in other Latin American countries" (Sorrilha, 2020). Furthermore, the political parties that emerged after independence, such as the Conservative Party and the Liberal Party, had their roots in the political factions formed during the presence of the Portuguese court, such as the Conservative Portuguese Party and the Liberal Portuguese Party.

This monarchical continuity and the evolution of political parties can be compared with governmental changes in other American countries, where independence led to new, more representative, albeit imperfect, forms of government. The following table summarizes these differences:

Country	Form of government Post-Independence	Popular participation (Vote)	Political parties
States United	Democratic Republic	All adult males (except slaves and indigenous people)	Federalists, Democrat-Republicans
Haiti	Republic	All adult men, especially former slaves	Local parties varied
Brazil	Monarchy Constitutional	Census vote (only men with income and land)	Conservative Party, Liberal Party
Mexico	Republic	Initially limited, slowly expanding	Local parties varied
Great Colombia	Republic	Excludes indigenous people and slaves	Bolívarists, Santanderistas
Cuba	Republic	Variable, with prolonged conflicts	Local parties varied

Argument 4: Nationalist Sentiment in Brazil

The fourth argument deals with nationalist sentiment in Brazil compared to other independence movements in America. The thesis is that Brazil did not develop a strong nationalist feeling immediately after independence, unlike what occurred in other countries.

In the United States, the American Revolution fostered a strong sense of national identity that was crucial to the cohesion of the new country. In Haiti, independence not only freed the country from colonial rule, but also created a nation where the majority of the population shared a common identity as former slaves. In Spanish America, although national identity has been more fragmented due to ethnic and cultural diversity, it is still

thus there was a significant drive to build a national identity after independence.

In Brazil, however, the development of nationalist sentiment was slower and less pronounced. During the government of Dom Pedro I, the focus was more on consolidating the power of the monarchy than on promoting a unified national identity. The creation of a stronger nationalist feeling only began to gain traction during the reign of Dom Pedro II, and even then, it was a gradual and uneven process.

Sérgio Buarque de Holanda highlights that "the process of building national identity in Brazil was slow and full of challenges, reflecting the country's social and regional complexity" (Holanda, 1936). The lack of a profound social revolution during independence contributed to this difficulty in creating a feeling of national unity.

Furthermore, the political and social structure of post-independence Brazil, with its census vote and centralization of power, made it difficult for the population to participate broadly in the formation of a national identity. Marcos Sorrilha observes that "regional fragmentation and the continuity of elitist power prevented the development of a strong and cohesive nationalist feeling in Brazil" (Sorrilha, 2020).

Separatist Revolts During the Regency Period

The regency period, which followed the abdication of Dom Pedro I in 1831, was marked by several separatist revolts that highlighted fragmentation and the lack of a unified nationalist feeling. During the regency, Brazil was governed by regents while Dom Pedro II was still a minor, creating a power vacuum that fostered regional dissatisfaction.

Some of the major separatist uprisings include:

Cabanagem (1835-1840): Occurred in Pará, it was a movement of popular insurrection against the central government, led by indigenous people, slaves and mestizos, reflecting dissatisfaction with socioeconomic conditions and the centralization of power.

Farroupilha (1835-1845): Also known as the Farroupilha Revolution, it took place in Rio Grande do Sul. It was a republican and separatist revolt against the imperial government, reflecting dissatisfaction with fiscal policy and the centralization of power.

Sabinada (1837-1838): Occurred in Bahia, it was a revolt led by military and civilians who sought the temporary separation of the province until Dom Pedro II reached the age of majority.

Balaçada (1838-1841): Revolt that occurred in Maranhão, led by country people and slaves against local elites and the central government, reflecting dissatisfaction with living conditions and the lack of political representation.

These revolts highlight the lack of a unified nationalist sentiment in Brazil during the Regency period, with several regions seeking greater autonomy or even separation from the central government. The existence of these separatist revolts suggests that, for many, Brazil's independence did not bring true integration or a sense of national identity.

Comparison with Other Countries

The following table summarizes the differences in the development of nationalist sentiment between Brazil and other American countries:

Country	Feeling Post-Nationalist Independence	Contributors to the National Identity	Revolts Separatists
States United	Strong and immediate	American Revolution, Declaration of Independence	None significant
Haiti	Strong and immediate	Slave revolt, creation of a free nation	None significant
Brazil	Slow and gradual	Centralization of power, census vote, regional fragmentation	cabinage, Farroupilha, Sabinada, Balaiada
Mexico	Moderate, development to over time	Social revolution, struggle against domination Spanish	Several, including War of the Cristeros
Great Colombia	Fragmented, variations regional	Independence struggles, ethnic diversity and cultural	Regional separatism after independence
Cuba	Strong, especially after conflicts prolonged	Fight for independence, Cuban cultural identity	None significant

Argument 5: Economic Impacts of Independence

The fifth argument examines the economic impacts of Brazil's independence, highlighting how economic changes were less pronounced compared to other independence movements in America. The thesis is that Brazil's economic structure remained relatively stable, with few significant changes after independence.

Economic Continuity in Brazil

One of the main reasons for economic continuity was Brazil's elevation to the status of the United Kingdom of Portugal, Brazil and Algarves in 1815. The opening of the ports in 1808, followed by the transfer of the Portuguese court to Rio de Janeiro, had already begun a economic reconfiguration that reduced dependence on the colonial pact. These changes allowed Brazil to develop a more autonomous economy and integrated with international trade even before formal independence in 1822.

Sérgio Buarque de Holanda observes that "the economic structure of post-independence Brazil reflected a continuity of the patterns established during the presence of the Portuguese court, with few significant changes" (Holanda, 1936). Maintaining the economy based on

Export agriculture, especially coffee and sugar production, continued to be the backbone of the Brazilian economy.

Economic Impacts on Other Countries

In contrast, other American colonies experienced more drastic economic changes after their independence. Below, we detail some of the main transformations in four countries:

U.S:

The American Revolution not only freed the colonies from British rule, but also triggered a series of significant economic changes. Industrial development began to accelerate, with the construction of factories and the introduction of new technologies. Westward expansion opened up vast lands for agriculture, mining, and settlement. This period also saw the creation of a robust financial system, including the establishment of the Bank of the United States.

Haiti:

Haitian independence resulted in one of the most radical economic changes of the time. The abolition of slavery completely transformed the country's agrarian structure. Large plantations were redistributed and began to be operated by small landowners and self-sufficient agricultural communities. Although this transformation had negative short-term effects on the country's production and economy, it represented a significant break with the colonial and slave past.

Mexico:

In Mexico, independence led to a series of land reforms and economic modernization. During and after the War of Independence, large rural properties (haciendas) were confiscated and redistributed. This included the nationalization of Church lands and redistribution to peasants. Additionally, Mexico began to develop its local industries and promote infrastructure, such as roads and railroads, to facilitate internal and external trade.

Gran Colombia:

The independence of the regions that formed Gran Colombia (currently Colombia, Venezuela, Ecuador and Panama) brought economic fragmentation, but also some significant reforms. In particular, there were efforts to diversify the economy beyond export monoculture. The production of coffee, cocoa, and other agricultural products began to expand, and there were attempts to promote local manufacturing. However, wars of independence and subsequent internal conflicts hampered short-term sustainable economic progress.

Comparative Table of Economic Impacts

The following table summarizes the differences in post-independence economic impacts between Brazil and other American countries:

Country	Post-Economic Impacts Independence	Significant changes
States United	Industrial development, westward expansion	Economic transformation and territorial expansion
Haiti	Land redistribution, subsistence economy	Abolition of slavery, radical agrarian changes
Brazil	Continuity of the export economy, stability	Few significant changes, economic continuity
Mexico	Land redistribution, economic modernization	Agrarian reform, beginning of industrialization
Great Colombia	Economic fragmentation, regional impact	Agricultural diversification and attempted industrialization

Analysis

In Brazil, the economic reforms that could have been expected after independence were limited. Although independence brought some additional economic opportunities, the fundamental structure of the economy remained unchanged. Slavery continued to be a central part of the economy until its abolition in 1888, and the agrarian elite maintained its control over key economic sectors.

Marcos Sorrilha points out that "Brazilian independence did not result in a significant economic transformation, reflecting the continuity of colonial practices and structures" (Sorrilha, 2020). This economic continuity highlights how Brazil's independence was more a reconfiguration of political power than a true social and economic revolution.

Conclusion

Brazil's independence, which occurred in 1822, differs significantly from other emancipation processes in America, not only due to the nature of the conflict and the political structures that followed, but also due to its economic continuity and the absence of a strong immediate nationalist feeling. This article has presented a detailed analysis of these aspects, arguing that Brazilian independence can be better understood as a reconfiguration of power within the Portuguese monarchy, rather than a revolutionary rupture.

Brazil's status as the United Kingdom of Portugal, Brazil and the Algarves since 1815 had already begun a transformation that differentiated Brazil from the other American colonies. The centralization of power in Rio de Janeiro and the maintenance of monarchical structures after independence, including the creation of the Moderating Power in the 1824 Constitution, reinforced the continuity of elitist control.

The Brazilian War of Independence involved relatively low popular participation and an extension of the conflict to Portugal, a unique phenomenon among American independences. The analysis of separatist revolts during the regency period, such as Cabanagem and the Farroupilha Revolution, demonstrated regional fragmentation and the lack of a cohesive nationalist feeling.

Economically, post-independence Brazil saw few significant changes, maintaining an export economy structure centered on agriculture. In contrast, other American countries have experienced more profound economic transformations, such as industrial development in the United States, land redistribution in Haiti, agrarian reforms in Mexico, and economic diversification efforts in Gran Colombia.

This analysis highlights that Brazil's independence was more of an internal adjustment within the existing structure than a true revolutionary transformation. The continuity of monarchical power and agrarian elites, political centralization and economic stability highlight the particularities of the Brazilian case in comparison with other American independences.

In short, Brazil's independence represents a unique case of political emancipation that maintained many of the structures of the colonial period, reflecting the country's internal complexities and dynamics. This continuity helps explain subsequent difficulties in building a unified nationalist sentiment and promoting significant economic change.

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Afterword - Unraveling the mystery stated at the beginning of the article:

If you got this far after reading the entire article, and probably even forgot my original text in the preface then I was successful. However, if you came to read the afterword after reading the preface then unfortunately you will miss the chance to make this discovery at the right time.

Although I, Leandro Villela de Azevedo, PhD in social history from USP, am effectively the author of this article, this is not my area of expertise, but rather the Middle Ages and cultural history. I have already produced several articles and those interested can check my Lattes CV at <http://lattes.cnpq.br/4582146701402549> or have access to all my work in <https://linktr.ee/Leandrovillela>

The secret of this article is that it is actually a test of the use of artificial intelligence tools for academic writing, after taking some courses, including open courses at USP. The tool used for this production was a mix of ChatGPT 4 from open.ai with the ScholarGPT Plugin from awesomegpts.ai – there was the possibility of using other tools that could “remove the detection of text produced by AI” since at the same time using the word choice algorithm to produce the text, the AIs of our generation (2024) still have characteristics in common in terms of word choices being more easily detectable.

As the objective of this article was not to produce an article about Brazil's independence but rather about the use of AIs for scientific production, I also make available to those interested the original “conversation” that generated the text as well as the modifications that were made. for textual improvement, and can be consulted at <https://chatgpt.com/share/31b325fe-160a-4f36-9e14-34cf794c56a4> (In Portuguese)

I apologize to the unsuspecting readers of the article for not having warned about this assumption in the beginning of the text. But according to the test proposed by Alan Turing, back in the 1950s, the power of an AI would be measured by the inability of a human interacting with it to distinguish it from another normal human. So what I would like is for all those who were able to reach this afterword to be able to somehow, preferably not organized and natural, talk about their textual perceptions, if for some reason they felt some kind of strangeness, as if it were not a text produced by a human, or if this perception was not awakened at any point during the reading.

Despite not being a text about Brazilian Independence, the ideas and arguments here presented were originally dictated by me, and the entire script and even the choice of some of the articles cited here were also my choice, with the aim of writing text that could follow the line of thought that I had determined, not just letting the AI would produce the text by itself. GPTS are just Pre-Trained Generators, that is, they combine words based on a training of billions of texts previously given to them and, according to a probability algorithm, they place the words into a text that seems intelligible to us. But they do not have an inherent intelligence in the ability to create their own original ideas (at least not for now, perhaps this technology will emerge soon) – This way, anyone who wants to read the way in which I instructed the creation of the text, will be able to see the step by step in the last link.

I am now available for contact here at Academia.edu (the place chosen by me for the official publication of the article) or through my social and contact networks indicated in the link provided above, or via email professorleandrovillela@gmail.com

I thank everyone for contributing their insights. And for anyone interested in more information about the use of AIs, or history, any contact with fellow researchers will be most welcome.